

Women Enrolment in Higher Education

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Abstract

Education is a notably widespread term consisting of various stages, from schooling or elementary learning to the development of specialized ability and competence. Focused skills, knowledge, and capability come throughout Higher Education. By attaining Higher Education, the person becomes well-organized enough to different social, economic, moral, and cultural issues. In India, “Right to Education” has become the ruling of the land, but still, Higher Education is to achieve a lot. The most significant problem is gender disparity about individuals willing to attain Higher Education. The norms of the patriarchal culture, even during the 21st century, exclude women from making up for Higher Studies. The gender gap is evident from the Higher Education enrolment ratio for men and women. The typecast in opting for faculties for Higher Studies also indicate that field of study has also become gender-specific. This paper particularly focuses on the enrolment aspect of Higher Education and analyzes the trend widespread with regards to gender inequality in Enrolment for Higher Education.

Keywords: Higher Education, Gross Enrolment Ratio, women enrolment, Women Education.

Introduction

Getting educated is no more an option; it has become a call for worldwide. It is understood that if anyone is born as a human being, she needs to be educated to become a better person who, in turn, will make valuable additions to their own lives and society. In India, special efforts are being made by the Government to ensure that every member of the nation has easy access to education. Predominantly, the Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-2017) is measured to be a big push in terms of ‘Education’ where the targeted efforts would also lead to improved enrolments. The 12th plan Document fixed a target of 25.2 percent Gross Enrolment Ratio by 2017-2018 and 30 percent Gross Enrolment Ratio by 2020-2021. All India Survey on Higher Education 2017-2018, the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education had increased from 24.5 percent in 2015-2016 to 25.8 percent in 2017-2018.

Taking concerning Women 'Education' would act as a method in their status upliftment. Since the Vedic period, women's education has been the most essential worry in India. Women are always without access to education, which further leads to decreased empowerment and the right to obtain decisions along with influence to guide. The Major reason for all this was the social structure of the country where women were treated as inferior to their counterparts.

Objectives

- To find out the Enrolment rates of Women in Higher Education.
- To know about the Gross Enrolment Ratio in Higher Education women.

Methodology

This study is based on a descriptive design. The Women's enrolment rate in Higher Education, and Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education for Women of the data collected from the Ministry of Human Resource Development 2015-16.

Women Enrolment in Higher Education

The act of putting yourself on to the official list of members of a course, college (or) university. The below table explains the women's enrolment of higher education.

Table 1 Women Enrolment of Higher Education (Student)

Female Student Enrolment per 100 Male Enrolment in Higher Education		
Sl.No	Year	Women Enrolment rate (per 100 Males)
1	2005-06	62
2	2006-07	62
3	2007-08	63
4	2008-09	65
5	2009-10	67
6	2010-11	78
7	2011-12	80
8	2012-13	81
9	2013-14	85
10	2014-15	85

Source: Ministry of HRD 2015-16

Table 1 inferred that the enrolment of women per 100 men in Higher education in India. During the year 2005-2006, women enrolment rate 62 and in the year 2014-2015 women enrolment rate 85.

Gross Enrolment Ratio

Gross Enrolment Ratio is the number of students enrolled in higher education. The below table explains the gross enrolment of women.

Table 2 The Gross Enrolment Ratio of Women

Sl.No	Year	The Gross Enrolment Ratio of Women
1	2006-07	10.0
2	2007-08	10.7
3	2008-09	11.4
4	2009-10	12.7
5	2010-11	17.9
6	2011-12	19.4
7	2012-13	20.1
8	2013-14	22.0
9	2014-15	23.2
10	2015-16	23.5

Source: Ministry of HRD 2015-16

Table 2 shows the Gross Enrolment Ratio of women during 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. During the year 2006-07, the Gross Enrolment Ratio of women in Higher Education has been increasing continuously over the years from 10 percent in 2006-07 to 23.5 percent in 2015-16.

Conclusion

The enrolment of women rate in Higher Education visibly shows that improvement has happened over the years with regards to taking into consideration specialized education as a significant part of 'Women Development'. Accurate indicators like Gross Enrolment Ratio make it understandable that women are affecting on the course of attaining Higher Education, other than the pace at which it experiences is not strong adequate to cover up the femininity disparity and show the way the country towards sustainable improvement. Away of all the learned women, barely a handful has obtained exacting education to acquire economic freedom. completely significant that the competent Human Resource be necessary for the development of the national Government, and related Ministries are serious level best to provide sufficient opportunities for Higher Education to Young India then what restrains us from getting our women enrolled for upper Studies, and gave more meaning to their existence when we know how to do the same of our male lot.

References

1. Anindita Chakrabarti A., 'Determinants of Participation in Higher Education and Choice of Disciplines: Evidence from Urban and Rural Indian Youth' South Asia Economic Journal Vol: 10, Iss: 2 pp: 371-402, 2009.
2. Mary E. John, 'Gender and Higher Education in the Times of Reforms', Contemporary Education Dialogue, Vol: 9, Iss: 2, Jul 18, 2012.
3. <https://pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=1541358>.